

Having realized its potential for improving the educational practice NCERT has started the National ICT Award for school teachers. This award is given annually to the school teachers for innovative use of technology in learning

Digital Learning Interface

In common parlance, the word “Digital learning Interface” has broad and varied meanings. It offers new ways for teachers and students to engage in the teaching-learning process. In a digital learning interface, the delivery hardware can range from desktop computers or laptops to tablets or smartphones, but the instructional goal is to support individual learning or organizational performance goals. In digital learning, courses are delivered via digital devices using words in the form of printed text or spoken and pictures such as animation, or video. It allows the individual learner to access training at any time or any location on their own. Since the use of ICT in education, there has been an ongoing debate as to the different resources of teaching and learning.

The Government of India through its national ICT policy in education along with many other initiatives under digital India is moving ahead to transform the educational practices, creating resources, providing infrastructure, and training the teachers and teacher educators. The following popular digital learning interfaces are available for effective pedagogical practices.

- SWAYAM (Study Webs of Active-Learning for Young Aspiring Minds), is a program initiated by the Government

of India. This effort aims to take the best teaching-learning resources to all, including the most disadvantaged. All courses are available free of cost for learning. In case the learner requires a verified certificate, a small fee will be applicable.

- E-Basta: In line with the government's Digital India initiative, C -DAC has created a framework to make school books accessible in digital form as e-books to be read and used on tablets and laptops.
- E-Pathshala, Government's Digital India initiative, has been developed by NCERT. The main idea is to bring various publishers and schools together on one platform for disseminating all educational e-resources including “textbooks, audio, video, periodicals, and a variety of other print and non-print materials through website and app. Students, teachers, educators, and parents can access e-books through multiple technology platforms.
- NPTEL (The National Programme on Technology Enhanced Learning), a project sponsored by the Ministry of Human Resource Development was first conceived in 1999 to pave the way for introducing multimedia and web technology to enhance the learning of basic science, math, and engineering concepts.
- National Digital Library of India is designed to hold the content of any language and provides interface support for leading vernacular languages. It is being arranged to provide support for all academic levels including teachers, researchers, and learners. All popular

forms of access devices and differently-abled learners.

- NMEICT (The National Mission on Education through Information and Communication Technology), has been envisaged as a Centrally Sponsored Scheme to harness the potential of ICT, in the teaching-learning process for the benefit of all the learners in Higher Education Institutions at anytime, anywhere and any mode.
- NROER (The National Repository of Open Educational Resources) is a collaborative platform, which brings together everyone interested in school and teacher education. It offers digital and digitized resources (audio, video, interactive images, and documents) in different languages along with online activities.

DLI and Teaching-learning

While the introduction of e-Learning and other digital technologies in some higher education institutions of learning has yielded positive results, the birth of interactive learning has called into question the acceptance of such teaching tools and the new roles that teachers have to play (Lu J & Yao JE, 2014). Digital learning interface (DLI), use is rapidly permeating every aspect of contemporary university life. It provides new ways of engaging with each other, with information, and with the world; we have pointed to both promising and problematic implications of these affordances. Educational technology has the potential to improve teaching-learning practices in education; however, the integrated use of technology in education is a complex system. In the last decade, educational

technology has made only modest inroads into changing teaching in schools and universities (Moser, 2007).

A teacher equipped with digital technologies can nurture divergent thinking, innovation, critical analysis, and scientific temper among the students to transform them into life-long learners and innovators. Oskouei (2010) internet is useful to both students as well as teachers if it is as a tool of knowledge creation and dissemination.

Many studies have been conducted on digital learning and ICT. According to the findings of Jones and Shao (2011) students prefer the moderated use of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) in their courses, viewing the use of course management systems, e-books, and online libraries positively; along with the use of new technologies such as blogs, wikis and 3D virtual worlds, the students positively respond to the incorporation of innovative technologies into the teaching and learning process provided that the technology used is well-conceived, purposeful and properly integrated into the teaching-learning process.

A review of online learning by Tallent-Runnels (2006) overwhelming evidence has shown that learning in an online environment can be as effective as that in traditional classrooms. Second, students' learning in the online environment is affected by the quality of online instruction. Clark and Mayer (2016) have reported growth from approximately 11 percent technology-

delivered instruction in 2001 to around 39 percent in 2011–2013 (ATD, 2014). Previous studies have pointed out that digital learning interfaces provide a platform to access digital resources for a person with special needs, such as those with visual or hearing impairments, learning or cognitive disabilities. It should be leveraged to help teachers shift from transferring information to facilitating learners to create knowledge and help them to shift from an acquisition mode of learning to one that engages in higher-order thinking, innovation, creativity, and collaboration.

E-learning is an important tool for learners. The 9.7% growth rate in the number of college and university students enrolled in at least one online class reported significantly exceeded the 1.5% growth rate in the overall higher education student population during the same period (Brady, et al, 2010). Rutherford (2010) examined that there is a positive relationship between academic uses of technology and the occurrences of active and collaborative learning and the frequency of student-faculty interactions. The educational performance of the students can be influenced positively or adversely by the use of technology such as the internet which is one of the most important factors in the 21st century (Mahamat, Rahim, and Oye, 2012).

The National Curriculum Framework for Teacher Education (NCFTE, 2009) considered among other things the Issues related to ICT in schooling as well as e-learning are in the center stage. The report states that ICT

despite its potential to make learning liberating, implementation is often not more than cosmetic. The curriculum recommends the inclusion of ICT as an important curricular resource, according to primacy to the role of the teacher, ensuring public ownership of digital resources, and promoting constructivist approaches that privilege anticipation and co-creation over mere access to it. A meta-analysis by Bernard et al. (2004) integrating research studies that compared learning from electronic distance education to learning from traditional classroom instruction yielded the achievement effect, indicating no practical differences in learning between face-to-face and electronic distance learning.

Conclusion

The Digital learning interface seems to have a profound impact on the process of learning in schools and higher education by offering new possibilities for teachers and learners. It can provide many advantages for teaching and learning innovations. In addition, although many schools and higher education institutions have invested a lot in hardware, the educational technology application in teaching and learning is still quite limited. Creating a support system that facilitates the creation, use, and management of DLI. It is the first stage in harnessing the full potential of DLI. There is a necessity to equip all teachers with the necessary DLI skills and knowledge on the appropriate pedagogical use of ICT in teaching and learning. Digital Learning Interface permits teachers to teach less and learners to learn more.

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